

Alkali Metal Complexes. Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with Picolinic Acid and Quinaldinic Acid

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Manuscript received 17 May 1983, accepted 3 June 1985

A number of mixed ligand complexes of alkali metal salts of some organic acids with picolinic acid and quinaldinic acid have been synthesised and characterised. They have the general formula $ML.HL'$, where, $M=Li, Na$ or K ; L =deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or *o*-nitrophenol, and HL' =picolinic acid or quinaldinic acid. Their IR spectra suggest the coordination of the alkali metals through oxygen atom of the COOH group as well as nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic ring.

MIXED ligand complexes in which picolinic acid acts as a secondary ligand are comparatively less studied. In one such report¹, stability constants of its mixed ligand complexes have been correlated with the vacant coordination sites after reaction of the metal with primary ligands. Literature survey reveals that although the pure neutral alkali metal complexes² of picolinic acid and the chelating behaviour of quinaldinic acid³ have been investigated, no such alkali metal complex in which they serve as secondary ligands, has been reported.

In this paper, we report the synthesis and characterisation of a number of mixed ligand complexes of alkali metal salts with the title ligands. They have the general formula $ML.HL'$, where $M=Li, Na$ or K ; L =deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) or *o*-nitrophenol (ONP); and HL' =picolinic acid (HPicA) or quinaldinic acid (HQuinA).

Experimental

An excess of HL' was added to a suspension of ML in absolute ethanol and then refluxed for ~0.5 h with constant stirring. The clear solution so obtained was concentrated and cooled, when characteristically coloured adduct separated. It was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and then dried in an electric oven at 80°. Lithium 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate and sodium oxinate did not form adducts with picolinic acid. It would be interesting to note that the ease of complexation of alkali metal salts with the ligands increased from Li to K. Yield too showed similar trend. Thus, in case of potassium, the complex separated quantitatively

even in cold. Actually, in most cases, the complex began to separate in cold.

The complexes could also be obtained by reversing the process, *i.e.* by refluxing alkali metal salts of HL' with 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or *o*-nitrophenol in ethanol. This is in consonance with the observation of Banerjee *et al.*⁴ that the pK value of a ligand cannot be regarded to be a dominant factor in the formation of alkali metal complexes.

Results and Discussion

The complexes of these ligands (HPicA and HQuinA) with alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline are yellow, brownish green and white, respectively. All the complexes gave satisfactory metal, C, H and N analyses. All the complexes are stable under dry conditions. They are soluble in most polar solvents, but are insoluble in non-polar solvents, such as benzene, toluene and diethyl ether. They either decompose or undergo transformation at temperatures considerably higher than the melting point of the ligand (HPicA, 135°/HQuinA, 156-58°), indicating thereby greater thermal stability of the complexes.

Infrared spectra: Infrared spectral measurements for the ligands and their mixed ligand alkali metal complexes were made between 400-650 cm^{-1} in nujol.

The broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} in HPicA and the multiple bands at 2700-1800 cm^{-1} in HQuinA disappeared in the spectra of the complexes, except

in the case of NaONP.HPicA. However, the spectra of all the complexes exhibit a broad band of medium intensity at 2350 cm^{-1} (in HPicA complexes) or at 2340 cm^{-1} (in HQinA complexes), except KONP.HQinA in which this band appears at 2540 cm^{-1} . These bands could be assigned to $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}/\text{N}\cdots\text{H}-\text{O}$ absorption and suggest hydrogen bonding to be a dominant factor in stabilising these complexes. The spectra of complexes of alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline with the ligand HQinA exhibit broad band at $3340\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ also, in addition to the 2340 cm^{-1} band.

The shifting of 1650 and 1520 cm^{-1} bands of the ligand HPicA to lower frequency by $5\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $10\text{--}12\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively in almost all its complexes, as well as shifting of the 1600 cm^{-1} band to higher frequency by $5\text{--}15\text{ cm}^{-1}$, suggest the coordination of HPicA with the alkali metals through carboxylic acid moiety. The medium intensity 1680 cm^{-1} band of the ligand HQinA shifted to lower frequency by $10\text{--}38\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in almost all the complexes. The splitting in case of its complexes with alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol appears to be due to the simultaneous presence of the coordinated N-O group of the primary ligand as well as the coordinated OH group of the carboxyl moiety of quinaldinic acid in them. The 1620 and 1560 cm^{-1} bands of the ligand too, in almost all the complexes, have shifted to lower frequency by $5\text{--}10$ and 5 cm^{-1} , respectively. The 1535 cm^{-1} band, which appears in medium intensity in the spectrum of HQinA, shows a steady shift of 7 cm^{-1} towards higher frequencies in the complexes. These features suggest the coordination of the ligand with the alkali metals through oxygen atom of the carboxyl moiety.

The 1580 cm^{-1} band of the ligands, assigned to the stretching $\text{C}=\text{N}$ absorption, shifted towards higher frequency by $5\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes. Only in case of the complexes of these ligands with alkali metal oxinates, it has split into two-one appearing towards higher frequency and the other towards lower frequency side. In all probability, this splitting is due to the simultaneous presence of $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ moiety in the quinoline ring of alkali metal oxinate as well as in the pyridine

ring of the ligand. These features suggest the coordination of the ligand with alkali metals through its ring nitrogen atom.

Conductivity: Molar conductance of all the complexes were measured in methanol at 25° at a concentration of 10^{-2} M .

A value of $35\text{--}40\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ corresponds to a 1:1 electrolyte⁵. From the results, it is evident that the molar conductance values of none of the complexes approach either ideal or a 1:1 electrolyte. However, fairly low values ($6.0\text{--}1.0\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) of their molar conductance suggest that the complexes are non-electrolyte.

Structure :

The above discussion suggests that both HPicA and HQinA behave as bidentate ligands in these complexes and that the coordination has taken place through oxygen atom of the COOH group as well as through nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic ring. The structure of complexes of HPicA ($\text{X}=\text{O}, \text{N}$) are shown below.

Similar are the structures of complexes of HQinA ($\text{X}=\text{O}, \text{N}$).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.P.S.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing financial assistance.

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